

The Dimensions of Users' Fun Experiences with Consumer Products

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Abstract

'Fun experience' is a component of user experience (UX) which has come to increased prominence in recent years. However, despite the research efforts, still there isn't any comprehensively constituted framework in the literature to explain what fun actually is. Therefore, this paper aims to reveal the dimensions of users' fun experiences by conducting two empirical studies. The first study examines the product qualities that play a role in fun experiences. The results were found to be categorized under three subject headings: tangible qualities, pragmatic qualities and hedonic qualities. The second study investigates the emotional content of the fun experiences, whose results indicated that the emotions of happiness/joy, contentment, interest and amusement are elicited most intensely throughout the experience. Studying the reasons behind the elicitation of these particular emotions revealed several fun-related product qualities, and also the high relevance of amusement and humor with users' fun experiences.

Conference theme: Modeling Experience

Keywords: fun, fun-related products, designing for fun

Introduction

User experience (UX) is a multi-dimensional user-product interaction that involves emotional usage. It extends the scope of the traditional usability in which it is referred to more than simplicity and ease of use, to encompass affect-based approaches to design. Design research is particularly interested in understanding the nature of UX, since experience underlies the basis of all user-product interactions. Hence, the researchers endeavor to develop this concept theoretically by building models (Alben, 1996; Hassenzahl, 2003; Wright, McCarthy, Meekison, 2003). The distinctions between these models arise from their focusing on different aspects of interaction. However, all of them attempt to complement a functional perspective on user-product interaction by adding sensual, emotional, social and cultural enhancements (Blythe, Wright, 2006).

There are some common dimensions of experience that each of these models investigate. For instance, these models refer to (1) physical and objective features of products contributing in experiences (*tangible qualities*), (2) the users' interpretation of these features in constructing their own image of products (*intangible qualities - pragmatic and hedonic*), (3) the affective consequences of interaction (*emotional content*), and (4) the influence of the *usage context* in which the experience unfolds. These common dimensions gathered from the models can be used for constituting the key elements of the UX concept (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The key elements of UX.

Fun can be considered as a sort of UX; consequently, all of the dimensions of UX are relevant for this experience as well. Blythe and Hassenzahl (2003) describe fun as an experience that distracts the person from the self in which his/her concerns and motivations are not relevant

during the experience. They further argue that fun experiences involve the elements of triviality and absurdness. Fun is associated with humor; consequently, the person is aware of the non-seriousness of the event. Certainly, these statements do not mean that fun-related products have to be cute and cheerful. Addressing fun should be done in a sophisticated way that goes beyond the superficial interpretations. In other words, fun should not be an afterthought; fun-related products should offer engagement in every level, which involve users physically and emotionally, appreciating their sensory richness (Overbeeke, Djajadiningrat, Hummels, Wensveen, Frens, 2003).

The literature survey reveals various studies investigating this subject; however these studies focus on positive experiences collectively and mostly explore the subject through computer applications and interfaces. Consequently, the literature lacks a study which particularly focuses on the users' fun experiences with 'products'. The studies presented in this paper aim to reveal the qualities of fun-related products in order to constitute an understanding on fun based on the framework presented in Figure 1.

Study 1: The tangible and intangible qualities of fun-related products

Method

In order to examine the fun-related qualities of products, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 39 participants (aged 22-48) who were chosen from the graduates of the Middle East Technical University, Department of Industrial Design. The participants were asked to describe attributes of products that they considered as fun, as well as attributes that in their view were not-fun. This was to check if the fun and not-fun aspects were actually polarized. Furthermore, it was thought that talking on concrete examples would be helpful for the participants to think of different aspects of the products. Therefore, they were then asked to give examples of fun products from their work places and homes along with an explanation of why they found these products to be fun.

Results

Each participant's considerations that played a role in their understanding of fun were listed on keyword level, which were used as the basis for the analysis. The keywords were content analyzed and categorized under three subject headings: tangible qualities, pragmatic qualities and hedonic qualities. These categories include the keywords that are related to fun-related and not-fun-related products together; which can be seen in Table 1.

		Intangible Qualities		Tangible Qualities
		Pragmatic Qualities	Hedonic Qualities	
fun (+)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multi-functionality (9) - Usability (8) - Usefulness (6) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Play/Interactiveness (22) - Originality/novelty (14) - Personalization (12) - Being associated with cute and humorous personalities (9) - Surprise factor (8) - Smartness (8) - Having references to pleasant memories (6) - Challenge (5) - Contributing to usage environment (5) - Being aesthetically pleasing (5) - Attention drawing (3) - Being relevant to hobbies (1) - Having references to toys & games (3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bright colors (18) - Organic form (7) - High-quality material (3) - Unexpected sound (4) - Mobility (5) - Having references to human body (5) 	
not- fun (-)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pure functionality (10) - Usability problems (17) - Non-functionality (19) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interaction problems (4) - Typicality (12) - Personalization problems(2) - Being associated with serious personalities (2) - Lameness (8) - Having references to unpleasant memories (3) - Being aesthetically unpleasing (6) - Being irrelevant to hobbies (2) - High-tech look (4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dark colors (6) - Cornered form (2) - Low-quality material (3) - Annoying sound (2) 	

NOTE: The numbers in the parenthesis indicates the number of participants mentioned that particular keyword

Table 1: The keyword categories.

Discussion

A. Pragmatic Qualities

- Fun-Related Aspects: *Multi-functionality* of the fun products was found to be a significant aspect within this category (9/39). Many participants expected their fun-related products to offer additional features. *Usability* (8/39) and *usefulness* (6/39) also appeared as other fun aspects in products. The products that provide physical and cognitive ease-of-use, and satisfy a functional need were given qualities of these kinds.

- Not-Fun Related Aspects: When it comes to the not-fun related aspects, this category gains considerable importance. The most significant factor in this category is the *non-functionality* of the products (19/39), which is followed by *usability problems* (17/39). These qualities were stated to be the pre-requisites before integrating fun aspects to the product design. Although they are extremely important for the products, *pure functionality* was not found to be enough by some participants (10/39). They suggested that fun-related products should offer some features beyond usefulness.

B. Hedonic Qualities

- Fun-Related Aspects: When the participants were asked about fun in relation to the products, the dominance of hedonic qualities was apparent. The *play factor* that the fun-related products involve and their *interactivity* were considered to be the most significant attribute of the study (22/39). The majority of the participants emphasized the importance of fluent interactions with the products; and expressed their desire to produce imaginative and creative usage scenarios with them. *Originality/novelty* is another significant aspect within this category, since the majority of the participants looked for distinctive and atypical properties in fun products (14/39).

Another attribute that the participants strongly related with the fun concept is *personalization* (12/39). The products that are unique, created or modified by their users, and reflect the characters of their users take place in this category. Furthermore, the products that are *cute* and comprise a *humorous character* (9/39), and have a *surprise factor* (8/39) were also considered to have fun aspects. Some participants mentioned that *smartness* built into products is also important and that fun products should have some well-thought and cleverly designed features (8/39).

As a more personal aspect, some participants mentioned that fun objects are *associated with pleasant memories*, reminding of past events, experiences or people (6/39). Some of them defined these products as being *aesthetically pleasing* (5/39), *challenging* (5/39) and making a *contribution to the usage environment* (5/39). Similarly, a few participants (3/39) regarded products as fun if they have *attention-drawing* aspects. Lastly, a *connection* of fun-related products to *hobbies* and their *references to toys and games* were also mentioned within this category by a few participants (1/39 and 3/39, respectively).

- Not-Fun Related Aspects: Conversely, when it comes to the (non)hedonic qualities of not-fun products, the keywords with opposite meanings are included. Within these, *typicality* was a major concern for the participants (12/39). Since uniqueness and novelty are very important in fun-related products, a typical appearance would decline the preferences when the product becomes widely available. *Lameness* was illustrated as another not-fun aspect (8/39) that refers to the products which do not offer any exciting attributes, and that are dull and monotonous. Furthermore, some participants (6/39) also evaluated not-fun-related products as being *aesthetically unpleasing*.

The products that do not allow any contribution of the users to the usage process and exhibit *interaction problems* were also considered as not-fun (4/39). A few participants stated their dislike of the *high-tech look* of the not-fun-related products (4/39), which were defined as

complex black boxes which do not impose any interactions for design. Lastly, a product's *references to unpleasant memories* (3/39), *association with a serious and formal character* (2/39), *personalization problems* (2/39), and *irrelevance to hobbies* (2/39) take part within this category.

C. Tangible Qualities

- Fun-Related Aspects: Within this category, *bright color* was the most mentioned aspect (18/39). *Rounded outlines* and *organic forms* were also found to summon up feelings of fun (7/39). Furthermore, some participants stated that fun is associated with products that have *references to human body* (5/39), indicating the reflection and incorporation of human-related attributes within products in a cartoon-like manner. While some participants (5/39) remarked that it could be fun for a product to exhibit *mobility* such as shaking, bouncing or revolving; some asserted that they enjoy the *unexpected sounds* that fun products make whilst in use (4/39). Lastly, a few participants mentioned that *material* is also important and that fun-related products should have a memorable texture and surface qualities (3/39).

- Not-Fun Related Aspects: In terms of not-fun aspects within the tangible qualities category, the keywords carry opposite meanings. In color, some of the participants associated *dark colors* with not-fun products (6/39); in form, *cornered and sharp outlines* were related with not-fun products (2/39). These two aspects together were asserted to be associated with seriousness, formality and high technology, in contrast with the fun-related products. A few participants also mentioned the *low-quality material* of the products (3/39) and their *annoying sounds* to be the not-fun related aspects (2/39).

Study 2: Emotional content of the fun experiences

Method

In order to reveal the emotions that are elicited during fun experiences, a questionnaire was applied to 23 participants (aged 16-33). In this questionnaire, the participants were asked to recall a 'fun experience' with a consumer product, write about this experience in detail and finally grade the intensity of the emotions they felt during this experience. The 36 emotions that appeared on the questionnaire had been taken from 'affect categories' of Scherer (2005). With respect to this study, some minor changes have been made in the original list (see Table 2). The questionnaire used in this study was not designed for providing an in-depth analysis on the subject; rather, it was aimed to determine the ranking for emotions elicited during fun experiences. The emotions that the participants gave the highest scores were later investigated

according to their appraisal dimensions with comprehensive literature research; and the findings were translated into product qualities.

Results

The grading of the participants was analyzed in terms of the average scores and standard deviations. These results can be seen in Table 2.

Happiness (cheerfulness, delight, enjoyment)	$M = 4.48$	s.d. = 0.79
Contentment (satisfaction)	$M = 4.43$	s.d. = 0.66
Amusement (humor, playfulness)	$M = 4.39$	s.d. = 0.84
Interest/Enthusiasm	$M = 4.39$	s.d. = 0.72
Joy (elation, exhilaration)	$M = 4.39$	s.d. = 0.84
Surprise (amazement, astonishment)	$M = 3.78$	s.d. = 1.17
Admiration/Awe (fascination, wonder)	$M = 3.74$	s.d. = 0.96
Desire	$M = 3.26$	s.d. = 1.42
Gratitude (thankfulness)	$M = 3.17$	s.d. = 1.15
Relaxation/Serenity (peacefulness, tranquility)	$M = 3.17$	s.d. = 1.37
Being touched	$M = 2.83$	s.d. = 1.27
Hope (optimism)	$M = 2.83$	s.d. = 1.19
Pride	$M = 2.65$	s.d. = 1.56
Relief	$M = 2.30$	s.d. = 1.36
Lust	$M = 2.09$	s.d. = 1.27
Nostalgia	$M = 1.96$	s.d. = 1.15
Envy	$M = 1.86$	s.d. = 1.42
Compassion (empathy, pity)	$M = 1.70$	s.d. = 0.97
Jealousy	$M = 1.70$	s.d. = 1.11
Humility	$M = 1.57$	s.d. = 1.08
Anxiety (nervous, worried)	$M = 1.39$	s.d. = 0.72
Contempt	$M = 1.27$	s.d. = 0.63
Guilt (blame)	$M = 1.26$	s.d. = 0.62
Tension/Stress (discomfort)	$M = 1.26$	s.d. = 0.62
Dissatisfaction	$M = 1.22$	s.d. = 0.42
Irritation (annoyance)	$M = 1.13$	s.d. = 0.34
Boredom	$M = 1.09$	s.d. = 0.29
Desperation (hopeless)	$M = 1.09$	s.d. = 0.29
Disappointment (disenchantment, frustration)	$M = 1.09$	s.d. = 0.29
Fear (afraid, fright, panic)	$M = 1.09$	s.d. = 0.29
Sadness (grief, melancholy, sorrow)	$M = 1.09$	s.d. = 0.29
Shame (embarrassment, humiliation)	$M = 1.09$	s.d. = 0.29
Anger (furious, madness, resentment)	$M = 1.04$	s.d. = 0.21
Disgust (aversion, detest, dislike, loath)	$M = 1.00$	s.d. = 0.00
Hatred	$M = 1.00$	s.d. = 0.00

Table 2: The average scores and standard deviations of the given emotions.

As can be seen in Table 2, fun experience was mostly associated with pleasant emotions and states. Within these, happiness, joy, contentment, interest/enthusiasm and amusement took the highest scores. Their relatively less standard deviations indicate that majority of the participants agree on the elicitation of these emotions during fun experiences. This attitude can also be seen in the negative emotions. On the other hand, the remaining emotions are context-specific. Their high standard deviations indicate that the elicitation of these emotions is specific to the

experiences that the participants have, depending on the usage environment, product qualities or usage process.

In order to understand the relation of the most intense emotions with fun-related products, it would be convenient to briefly mention the appraisals behind their elicitation before discussing the findings of the study. The appraisals of these emotions were collected from various studies in the psychology literature; and they are summarized in Table 3. It should be noted that, the emotions of happiness and joy combined in analysis since they are studied together within the literature and the ratings of the participants are parallel between these two emotions.

<i>Emotions</i>	Happiness/Joy	Contentment	Interest	Amusement
<i>Appraisal Types</i>	Motive consistency	Motive consistency	-	Motive consistency
	Pleasantness	-	Pleasantness	Pleasantness
	High level of certainty	-	Moderate certainty	-
	Circumstance caused	-	Controlled by the situation	-
	High control potential	-	Coping potential	Effort to cope with complexity
	-	Expectation confirmation	-	-
	-	-	-	Resolution of incongruity
	-	-	Novelty	Novelty
	-	-	-	Cues precluding seriousness
	-	-	-	Diminishing attribute

Table 3: The appraisal structures of happiness/joy, contentment, interest and amusement.

Discussion

When the appraisal structures of these four emotions are studied, amusement seems to be the most relevant emotion in fun elicitation. Happiness/joy, contentment and interest have an inferential relation to fun, whereas amusement has a direct effect on making the users smile. As a matter of fact, happiness is a generic response to all pleasant circumstances; instead of signifying a specific emotional state it is used for referring to most pleasant emotional experiences. Likewise, contentment is also a pleasant emotional state originating from an individual's expectation confirmations with an overall evaluation of a stimulus (Demir, 2007).

Therefore, it is convenient to say that these emotions are elicited during fun experiences because of their general pleasantness qualities; however, elicitation of these emotions is not limited solely to fun experiences. Similarly, interest does not necessarily contribute to all fun experiences as well. Interest's main function is to encourage the individuals to explore, collect information and learn about the environment (Silvia, 2005). Therefore, it may be stated that interest lies behind all of our interaction with the environment which is not specific to fun. The reasons behind the high scores of these emotions can also be discussed in terms of their common appraisal structures:

(1) The first common appraisal is *motive consistency*. This appraisal refers to the satisfaction of a need or attainment of a goal (Demir, 2007). In terms of product design, this appraisal signifies the functionality of products that helps a person to achieve something or satisfies a goal (Desmet, 2002).

(2) *Pleasantness* is another appraisal that refers to the attribute of the product that encourages a person to approach it (Scherer, 2001). The fun-related products motivate their users to move toward themselves; and they are the products that the users enjoy spending time with.

(3) Another appraisal dimension is *novelty*. The products which deviate from what we know (unfamiliar) and the ones that are discrepant with the users' expectations (unexpected) can be considered as the characteristics of fun-related products (Desmet, 2002).

(4) *Agency* appraisal refers to the thing/person/event responsible in that particular situation (Scherer, 2001). In fun experiences it is the product that leads to the elicitation of certain emotion, rather than the characteristics of the users.

(5) The person's ability to cope with the situation or *high control potential* is another appraisal that refers to the moderate complexity of the product and the user's capacity to deal with this complexity in terms of understanding or appreciating the product (Silvia, 2005).

These five appraisals are common between the emotions; however there are some other appraisal dimensions that are specific to each of them. The first one is *resolution of incongruity*. Incongruity may be found within the qualities of product itself (e.g. unrelated or contradictory elements) or in the usage context (e.g. irrelevance between product-environment, product-user); wherein the user should be able to understand and appreciate the incongruity (Rothbart, 1973, in Desmet, 2002). Another appraisal dimension of amusement is *cues precluding seriousness* which refers to the individual's awareness of the un-seriousness of the event (Apter, 1982, in Wyer, Collins, 1992). Fun-related products do not interfere with the user's goals and well-being; and encourage the users to interact inventively. *Diminishing attribute* is another unique appraisal that refers to the falsification of the initial interpretation of a stimulus by further information which diminishes the importance of this initial interpretation (Wyer, Collins, 1992).

When the true attributes of the product are less favorable than the way they are expected, this situation leads to amusement. The last emotion-specific appraisal dimension worth mentioning here is the *expectation confirmation* appraisal of contentment. Contentment requires an expectation match which is related with the desirable outcome that the users want to achieve with the products (Desmet, 2002).

Conclusions

‘Fun experience’ is a component of UX that has come to an increased prominence in recent years. Yet, there is not any comprehensively constituted framework in the literature to explain what fun actually is. In order to fill this gap, two empirical studies were conducted according to the UX framework that was derived from the review of the models found in the UX literature. When the findings of the studies are integrated into this framework, its extent is confined to the users’ fun experiences with consumer products (see Figure 2). Within this framework, the ‘usage context’ component has been omitted since it cannot be examined due to the time limitations.

Figure 2: The components of users’ fun experiences.

In terms of the tangible qualities, it surely cannot be expected from every product that takes place in fun experiences to possess all of these elements. Instead, they should be considered as common qualities shared by most products that are entitled as fun, which lead to fun-related associations of the users. The results of the study also specified the importance of pragmatic qualities as pre-requisites for attaining fun. It seemed that users’ fun experiences are provided when the hedonic qualities are added on the products to enhance their functionality and usability.

Furthermore, the results also indicated that happiness/joy, interest, contentment and amusement are elicited most intensely during fun experiences. However, the appraisal pattern of amusement exhibited its relatively higher relevance with users' fun experiences. The common appraisals behind these emotions were also found to be in parallel with the findings of the first study. For instance, the motive consistency appraisal corresponds to the 'usefulness', pleasantness appraisal matches with the 'play factor/interactiveness' attributes of the former study. These aspects refer to the products that satisfy a goal and motivate their users to spend time with, respectively. Besides, being novel was observed to be a significant result of both studies. Lastly, dealing with complexity appraisal is also echoed in the findings of the previous study in terms of 'challenge' attribute. The pragmatic quality of 'usability' also partly signifies this aspect as it refers to being able to cope with the product. Consequently, the studies have common results that verify the findings of each other.

The product attributes that have been mentioned in the related literature and by the participants in the present thesis constitute a valuable data for the product designers to understand users' perceptions and expectations in relation to fun. However, the designers' purpose cannot be designing a fun experience. The designers can only 'design for experience' (Wright, McCarthy, Meekison, 2003), indicating that they combine the appropriate product qualities to create the intended effect. By analyzing the users thoroughly and investigating their expectations and needs, the designers can 'design for fun experiences'. At the same time, research efforts like this study can be helpful to the designers in creating more successful, engaging and 'fun' products.

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References

- Alben, L. (1996). "Quality of Experience." *Interactions*, 3 (3), 12-15.
- Blythe, M. and Hassenzahl, M. (2003). "The Semantics of Fun: Differentiating Enjoyable Experiences." In M.A. Blythe, A.F. Monk, K. Overbeeke and P.C. Wright (Eds.), *Funology: from usability to enjoyment* (pp. 91-100). Netherlands: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Blythe, M.A. and Wright, P.C. (2006). "Pastiche scenarios: Fiction as a resource for user centred design." *Interacting with Computers*, 18, 1139-1164.

- Demir, E. (2007). "Interaction appraisals: Understanding and designing for user emotions." Internal paper, TU-Delft.
- Desmet, P.M.A. (2002). "Designing Emotions." Doctoral Thesis. TU-Delft.
- Hassenzahl, M. (2003). "The thing and I: Understanding the relationship between user and product." In M.A. Blythe, A.F. Monk, K. Overbeeke and P.C. Wright (Eds.), *Funology: from usability to enjoyment* (pp. 31-42). Netherlands: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Overbeeke, K., Djajadiningrat, T., Hummels, C., Wensveen, S. and Frens, J. (2003). "Let's Make Things Engaging." In M.A. Blythe, A.F. Monk, K. Overbeeke and P.C. Wright (Eds.), *Funology: from usability to enjoyment* (pp. 7-18). Netherlands: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Scherer, K.R. (2001). "Appraisal Considered as a Process of Multilevel Sequential Checking." In K.R. Scherer, A. Schorr, & T. Johnstone (Eds.), *Appraisal Processes in Emotion: Theory, Methods, Research* (pp. 92-120). New York: Oxford University Press.
- Scherer, K.R. (2005). "What are emotions? And how they can be measured?" *Social Science Information*, 44 (4), 695-729.
- Silvia, P.J. (2005). "What Is Interesting? Exploring the Appraisal Structure of Interest." *Emotion*, 5 (1), 89-102.
- Wright, P., McCarthy, J. and Meekison, L. (2003). "Making Sense of Experience." In M.A. Blythe, A.F. Monk, K. Overbeeke and P.C. Wright (Eds.), *Funology: from usability to enjoyment* (pp. 43-54). Netherlands: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Wyer, R.S. and Collins, J.E. (1992). "A theory of humor elicitation." *Psychological Review*, 99, 663-688.